

Beyond Unidirectional Drivers: Endogenizing IPAT in an Integrated Assessment Model

Abstract

This article revisits and extends the IPAT framework ($\text{Impact} = \text{Population} \times \text{Affluence} \times \text{Technology}$) by representing the IPAT equation in a dynamic and endogenized way within the system-dynamics model MORDRED. Unlike static interpretations of IPAT that treat each component as independent and unidirectional driver of environmental impact, our approach captures the complex, reciprocal interactions between population, affluence, technological development and environmental impacts over time. Through the simulation of a business-as-usual scenario, and a range of population-, sufficiency- and efficiency-related policy scenarios, we examine the systemic implications of these interdependencies for environmental sustainability and economic stability. Our results reveal three key insights. First, the components of the IPAT equation are deeply interrelated: changes in one driver dynamically influence the others, and can both slow down and reinforce environmental degradation. Second, in the absence of ambitious and stringent policy interventions or societal changes, these interactions accelerate environmental impacts, triggering biophysical feedbacks that in turn undermine economic and demographic stability, leading to systemic collapse. Third, although combined policy measures targeting all three drivers, especially population size, can significantly reduce environmental pressures, they are far from sufficient to achieve long-term environmental sustainability. The formal integration of dynamic IPAT relationships into an IAM provides a novel lens for assessing policy effectiveness and the behavior of different social and biophysical systems. Our findings underscore the continued relevance of IPAT but also point to the importance of a detailed analysis of the underlying global cultural, economic and political institutions that fundamentally condition and shape future evolutions of every IPAT component.

Keywords

Integrated Assessment Modeling; sustainability modeling; business as usual; sufficiency; world population; system dynamics.

1. Introduction

The *IPAT* identity emerged from a debate between Ehrlich, Holdren and Commoner in the early 1970s (Commoner, 1972; Ehrlich & Holdren, 1971, 1972) and has influenced decades of research on the anthropogenic driving forces of environmental impacts due to its relative simplicity and the clear decomposition of impact into three key variables. Over the years the original equation has been modified and re-evaluated by different authors (Chertow, 2000; McGee et al., 2015; Waggoner & Ausubel, 2002; Wei, 2011; York et al., 2003b), with the STIRPAT model being one of the most prominent extensions because it enables researchers to conduct statistical analyses of the causal linkages between anthropogenic drivers and environmental impacts by quantifying their relative weights in the equation (Dietz & Rosa, 1997; Rosa & Dietz, 1998). The *IPAT* framework has been used to study a wide range of environmental impacts, ranging from pollution such as CO₂ emissions in the Soviet Union (Brizga et al., 2013) to the water use of the economy (J. Yang & Chen, 2019) and waste generation at tourist destinations (Arbulu et al., 2017). Furthermore, it has been linked to other environmental accounting frameworks such as life-cycle accounting (Font Vivanco et al., 2014) and material flow analysis (Fischer-Kowalski & Amann, 2001), and has influenced the development of the Kaya identity promoted by the IPCC, and the master equation in industrial ecology (Chertow, 2000; Magee & Devezas, 2018).

Given that *IPAT* enables modelers to project environmental impacts under different assumptions regarding future changes in population, affluence and technology the framework has also been used in different modeling and scenario studies, including the quantification of economic scenarios beyond growth in Sweden (Skånberg & Svenfelt, 2022), the exploration of different land-use scenarios under SSP1 - SSP4 (Karlsson et al., 2018) and the development of country-level emission and socio-economic pathways through the downscaling of regional scenarios (Gütschow et al., 2021).

Nevertheless, since its initial formulation research interests and trends have led to a fundamental reinterpretation of the *IPAT* framework (Chertow, 2000): while *IPAT* was originally developed to illustrate the unsustainability of harmful technology, affluence in the developed countries and population growth, it has increasingly been used to emphasize the potential of green technologies and to examine the hypothesized positive effect of affluence on environmental degradation, as suggested by the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) (Xing et al., 2023; Zhao et al., 2017). Also, although Ehrlich and Holdren (1972) explicitly stated that the variables on the right-hand side of the identity are not independent from each other, many models only focus on the *affluence* → *technology* relationship shaping the EKC, rather than on other existing feedback dynamics between the drivers of environmental degradation. This is reflected in the technology-focus of current integrated assessment modeling: although integrated assessment models (IAMs) link demographic, economic, social and environmental systems, they often prioritize the identification of optimal technological pathways while sidestepping policies that would tackle affluence (Hickel et al., 2021; Wiedmann et al., 2020) and population growth (Alcott, 2012).

This paper introduces an IAM that reflects a reinterpretation of the *IPAT* equation stressing the interlinkages and feedback dynamics between the identity's components and the importance of considering a bidirectional causality between ecological and anthropogenic drivers and impacts. Our study makes three main contributions to the literature. First, we develop a dynamic and complex interpretation of the *IPAT* equation by disaggregating every component and formalizing different feedback relationships between the main drivers. Second, we endogenize the *IPAT*

equation in the IAM MORDRED, thereby illustrating that the structure of every coupled demographic-economic-environmental model can be interpreted and assessed through an *IPAT* lens. Last, we construct *IPAT*-informed policy scenarios and assess their isolated and combined effects on key variables of the global system.

2. Theoretical background and methods

In this section we describe different possible theoretical approaches to *IPAT*, the quantitative model, and the designed scenarios.

2.1. Possible theoretical approaches to *IPAT*

We distinguish four theoretical approaches to the *IPAT* identity that influence our modeling exercise.

Firstly, *IPAT* can be understood as a framework to disaggregate the drivers of environmental degradation and to analyze how changes in the different components over time affect the overall environmental impact, resulting in policy recommendations that can address *P*, *A* and *T* (Engström & Kolk, 2024).

$$I = P * A * T \quad (1)$$

Given that consumption is a share of economic output, *X* can be understood as total consumption or total economic production and influences both *A* and *T*.

$$A = \frac{X}{P} \quad (2)$$

$$T = \frac{I}{X} \quad (3)$$

Secondly, the *P-A-T* components can be seen as interdependent. For example, Alcott (2010) identifies nine simultaneous equations on the right-hand side of $I=PAT$ ($T=f(P)$, $A=f(T)$, $P=f(A)$ etc.).

$$I = f(P, A, T) \quad (4)$$

Thirdly, from a system dynamics perspective, the left- and the right-hand side of *IPAT* could mutually influence each other, and *I* can drive itself. For instance, environmental degradation can reduce the carrying capacity (Ehrlich & Ehrlich, 2013; Meadows et al., 1972) of global ecosystems, while climate tipping points (Armstrong McKay et al., 2022) serve as example of self-enforcing 'environmental degradation'.

$$\frac{dP}{dt} = f(P, A, T, I) \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = f(P, A, T, I) \quad (6)$$

$$f(P, A, T, I) = 0 \quad (7)$$

Last, adopting a critical or constructivist approach, it is possible to argue that P , A and T are first order drivers that are themselves shaped by underlying second order drivers including economic modes of productions (e), political governance institutions (g) and hegemonic cultures (c) (Mokyr, 2016; York et al., 2003a).

$$I(P, A, T) = f(P(e, c, g), A(e, c, g), T(e, c, g)) \quad (8)$$

This approach is difficult to represent explicitly within formal models but must be considered when designing and interpreting scenarios.

2.2. Operationalizing IPAT

IAMs provide an opportunity to formalize the *IPAT* components and their mutual interactions. Thus, they facilitate the systematic exploration of different policy interventions.

This section explains how the model used for this study represents *IPAT* and to which extent it considers complex feedback relationships between *IPAT* components.

2.2.1. Model structure

MORDRED (Model of Resource Distribution and Resilient Economic Development) is an IAM well suited for investigating IPAT-related questions because it provides detailed representations of population dynamics, affluence levels, technological change, and environmental impacts, alongside multiple feedback mechanisms that interconnect these drivers.

MORDRED's population module represents the global population, which is disaggregated into 3 world regions, 10 classes and 20 age groups. The 'center' includes the population living in high-income countries, the 'semiperiphery' the population residing in upper-middle-income countries and the 'periphery' the population of lower-middle- and low-income countries. Within every world region except the center, the population is assumed to either be sustained by the global economy or by subsistence economies. The populations belonging to the latter constitute the 'subsistence class' whereas the population living within the world economy is divided into 3 classes per world region: the Top20 (the richest 20%), the Bottom30 (the poorest 30%) and the Middle50 (the remaining 50% of the population). Differences between the per capita consumption of the subsistence class and the Bottom30 drive migration dynamics between the two economic regimes.

Economic production is represented using an Input–Output (IO) framework comprising 25 global economic sectors, including primary, secondary, and tertiary sectors as well as multiple energy technologies. Following the IO method (Miller & Blair, 2009), the model represents inter-industry flows and the production of intermediate goods through a 25x25 A matrix. Final demand is disaggregated into household and government final demand as well as investment. The sum of all demand components and intermediate goods yields global economic output (X).

A is modeled as consumption per capita. An individual's affluence depends on overall global economic development, on the world region and on the individual's class. Overall economic development, in turn, can be restrained by the availability of a series of input factors: labor hours, different types of land, capital, and intermediate products, notably from the energy sectors.

Technology is represented in MORDRED through the A matrix and through 'impact intensities' of production. The input coefficients of the A matrix indicate the technological profile of the economy. Declining input requirements, especially from energy sectors, typically reflect

technological progress via efficiency improvements, whereas rising input requirements may point to increasing challenges in extracting, processing, and transforming raw material (Brockway et al., 2019; Igogo et al., 2021; Norgate & Haque, 2010). Material extraction for different materials is computed through material intensity factors linked mainly to the output of the mining sector while fossil fuel intensity factors for the output of the fossil fuel sectors allow the model to calculate fossil resource demand.

Impacts on the biophysical environment resulting from economic activities and represented in MORDRED include different greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, extracted materials, increased land use changes through forest conversion, and increased air and soil pollution. For our simulation we activate feedbacks within the climate system that result in higher temperature increases for any given level of anthropogenic GHG emissions.

Adverse effects on the economic structure resulting from environmental degradation represented in MORDRED include climate change damages of capital stock, labor productivity, working force and input intensities of the food sector, as well as increasing input coefficients for the extraction of fossil fuel resources that reflect increasing depletion of the finite fossil resource stock which is estimated based on BGR data on coal reserves and oil and gas resources (2020). Given that the main motivation of this study is methodological and conceptual, we reduce the model's complexity by deactivating all climate impacts so that only the energy-depletion feedback remains active. As will be shown, this feedback mechanism is sufficient to illustrate key dynamics emerging from a system dynamics approach to *IPAT*.

A detailed explanation of MORDRED is provided in Lauer & Llases (2025).

2.2.2. Feedback relationships between I,P,A and T in MORDRED

Because of its system dynamic basis, MORDRED can represent many of the feedback relationships between the components of *IPAT*. The main causal relationships are:

- 1) $PAT \rightarrow I$: Different types of impacts result from multiplying the output of economic production (X) with conversion efficiencies T_j (j includes land, energy and CO₂). The output can be disaggregated into the population and affluence level of three regions r that each contain 3 consumption classes k , the government consumption of every region, the production of intermediate products Z , and gross fixed capital formation $GFCF$.
- 2) $I \rightarrow PAT$: Only the consequences of growing resource depletion are considered through an extraction difficulty factor (EDF) which is multiplied with the input coefficients of the fossil sectors (no. 3 and 8) of the A matrix (M); other impacts (e.g. damages from climate change, biodiversity loss etc.) are not considered although it is possible to represent them through the economic structure of the model. Direct impacts of damages on population and technologies are not represented in MORDRED.
- 3) $P \rightarrow A$: Consumption per capita is a function of total population size and economic output which in turn is a function of labor productivity T_L and labor supply. The latter depends on the size of the population aged 15-64, the participation rate (prt) and the hours worked ($whours$). Thus, both T_L and the age structure of the population determine affluence.
- 4) $A \rightarrow P$: The difference in the affluence of the poorest classes in the world economy (we) and of the people living in subsistence acts as a driver of migration dynamics between the population of the subsistence and the world economy, with higher affluence levels

acting as an attractor of population from the subsistence regime. Mortality and fertility rates follow an asymptotic pattern for most age groups a and decrease with affluence.

- 5) $P \rightarrow T$: Hypothesized effects of an increasing population size are not represented in the model.
- 6) $T \rightarrow A$: The model represents two effects of T on A . On the one hand, productivity improvements of the input factors (land, labor, energy) allow output to grow, which can rise consumption levels. At the same time, production technologies increasingly impact the environment in a negative way, which in turn negatively impacts economic production capacities, reducing affluence levels.
- 7) $T \rightarrow P$: The model represents two effects of T on P . On the one hand, land productivity increases allow for a stronger growth of the agricultural sector, leading to increased consumption, reduced mortality and a higher population. On the other hand, there is an indirect negative effect on population size through adverse impacts on the economy and reduced affluence levels that increase mortality rates.
- 8) $A \rightarrow T$: Input requirements to the production process are assumed to decrease with increasing final demand per capita, due to increased investments in research and education. In the model, T improves as a logarithmic function of A .

Table 1 illustrates how the feedback relationships are operationalized in the model while Figure 1 provides a graphical summary of the operationalization of *IPAT* components in MORDRED.

Dimension	Feedback relationship number	Model	
$PAT \rightarrow I$	1)	$I_j = \left[\left(\sum_{i=r}^3 \sum_{k=1}^3 P_{r,k} * A_{r,k} \right) + Z + \sum_{r=1}^3 C_{govr} + GFCE \right] * T_j$ <p>with $T_j = \frac{I_j}{X}$ and $I = \sum_{j=1}^n I_j$</p>	(9)
$I \rightarrow PAT$	2)	$M_{i,3t_{with\ impacts}} = M_{i,3t_{without\ impacts}} * EDF$ $M_{i,8t_{with\ impacts}} = M_{i,8t_{without\ impacts}} * EDF$ $EDF > 1$	(10)
$P \rightarrow A$	3)	$A = c_{per\ capita} = f(X(Labor, T_L), P)$ $Labor\ hours = Prt * whours * P_{working\ age}^{we}$	(11)
$A \rightarrow P$	4)	$Migration_{Sub \rightarrow we} = f(A_{we})$ $Mortality\ rate_a = \alpha_{MR} + (\beta_{MR} - \alpha_{MR}) * e^{-\gamma A}$ $Fertility\ rate_a = \alpha_{FR} + (\beta_{FR} - \alpha_{FR}) * e^{-\gamma A}$ <p>Except for $a_{[30;34]}$ and $a_{[35;39]}$</p>	(12)
$P \rightarrow T$	5)	-	(13)
$T \rightarrow A$	6)	$A = f(X(I), P)$ $\max(X) = \frac{J}{T_j}$ $I_j = T_j * X$	(14)

		$\frac{dX}{dt} < 0$ $T \rightarrow I \rightarrow A$	
$T \rightarrow P$	7)	$\max(X_{agriculture}) = \frac{\text{total land}}{T_{land}}$ $T_j * X = I_j$ $A = f(X(I), P)$ $\text{Mortality rate}_a = f(A)$ $T \rightarrow I \rightarrow A \rightarrow P$	(15)
$A \rightarrow T$	8)	$T_{intermediary\ products} = f(\beta_1 * \ln(A_t) + \beta_2)$	(16)

Table 1: Integration of IPAT in MORDRED.

Figure 1: Relationships between the elements of IPAT in the MORDRED model.

2.3. Scenarios

We explore how IPAT plays out in the model through one baseline and four policy intervention scenarios. The baseline scenario is designed to illustrate the feedback between the left- and the right-hand side of $I=PAT$ while the policy scenarios explore the consequences of politically motivated changes in one, several or all drivers.

- *Baseline/no policy intervention*: In this scenario there are no policy interventions and, consequently, P, A, T and I develop endogenously following the basic model calibration and dynamics.
- *Population policy intervention (PPI)*: In this scenario, a global one-child policy is adopted.

- *Sufficiency policy intervention (SPI)*: In this scenario, the per capita consumption of the whole world converges to the level of the Top20 of the semiperiphery until 2060.
- *Efficiency policy intervention (EPI)*: In this scenario, we assume that at any given level of GDP per capita, the material and energy intensity of the economy is 5% lower than it would be in the absence of a technology-focused policy intervention. Additionally, fossil electricity is completely replaced by renewable electricity while in the baseline scenario 10% of the original fossil electricity input into the production process is maintained.
- *Population & sufficiency policy intervention (PPI+SPI)*: This scenario combines the policies of PPI and SPI.
- *Population & efficiency policy intervention (PPI + EPI)*: This scenario combines the policies of PPI and EPI.
- *Sufficiency & Efficiency policy intervention (SPI+ EPI)*: This scenario combines the policies of SPI and EPI.
- *Integral policy intervention (IPI = PPI + SPI + EPI)*: This scenario combines all policies in the IPAT framework.

To simulate the scenarios, we developed MORDRED 1.0.3 which includes four main changes compared to MORDRED 1.0:

First, we introduced a ‘technological impact factor’ (*TIF*) that changes the energy and material input requirements (*EMIR*) in the A matrix and depends on global final demand per capita.

$$\text{Technological Impact Factor } (TIF)_t = \beta_1 * \ln\left(\frac{FD}{P_t}\right) + \beta_2 \quad (17)$$

$$EMIR_{EMsectors,sectors_t} = TIF_t * EMIR_{EMsectors,sectors_{2019}} \quad (18)$$

EM (energy & material) sectors include the sectors 3,4,10, 12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19 and 20 (Suppl.Table1).

The parameters β_1 and β_2 ensure that *TIF* takes a value of 1 for a world final demand per capita corresponding to the initial moment of the simulation (2019) and a value of 0 when world final demand per capita approaches a high level, corresponding to approximately 80,000 € per capita based on a statistical analysis of York et al. (2003b).¹ At this point, it is assumed that the affluence elasticity of impact reaches 0, and, consequently, energy input requirements to the economy reach zero. This assumption introduces two strong optimistic biases into the analysis: First, it implies that strong absolute decoupling and complete dematerialization of the economy is possible, which contradicts thermodynamic principles. Second, while the threshold value given in York et al. applies to the affluence elasticity of CO₂, we use the same value for the affluence elasticity of energy. However, absolute decoupling for CO₂ is easier to achieve than absolute decoupling of energy use, since impacts can be shifted (e.g. from emissions to increase land use and biodiversity loss) by substituting fossil fuels with other energy sources, while overall energy intensity remains unchanged.

Second, we added an efficiency multiplier (M_{EPI}) that represents the effects of policy interventions aiming at accelerating the speed of technology-driven efficiency improvements:

$$TIF_{t_{EPI}} = (\beta_1 * \ln(\text{final demand per capita}_t) + \beta_2) * M_{EPI} \quad (19)$$

¹ The threshold value given in York et al. was converted to 2019-€.

In the EPI scenario and all other scenarios with an EPI component, the multiplier is set to 0.95, i.e. policies are assumed to accelerate the process of dematerialization by 5% at every level of economic development.

Third, we introduced the possibility to alter annual birth rates (BR) in all the regions and age groups in the model exogenously, approximating the effects of regional and/or global population policies. To simulate a global one-child policy, the sum of the birth rates over all age groups is set to 0.5, i.e. every adult has on average 0.5 children during the reproductive age (15-44 years).

$$BR_{age\ group,region_t} = \frac{1}{5} * \frac{1}{2} * \frac{BR_{age\ group_{i_{2019,region}}}}{\sum_{i=1}^6 BR_{age\ group_{i_{2019,region}}} \quad (20)$$

Last, we added the option to let the consumption per capita of all classes converge toward the level of the richest 20% of the semiperiphery ($c_{T20,semip.}$) by defining exogenous growth rates ($g_{class,region}$).

$$g_{class,region_t} = e^{\ln\left(\frac{c_{T20,semip.2019}}{c_{class,region_{2019}}}\right)} - 1 \text{ if } c_{class,region_t} \neq c_{T20,semip.} \quad (21)$$

$$g_{class,region_t} = 0 \text{ if } c_{class,region_t} = c_{T20,semip.} \quad (22)$$

The Supplementary Material contains the parametrization of all scenarios that are simulated for the period 2019 - 2110.

3. Results

This section includes the key results and main insights from all scenario simulations realized in MORDRED. First, we present the simulation outcomes of the Baseline scenario which serves as a reference for the isolated policy interventions (PPI, SPI and EPI). Subsequently, we compare the development of *IPAT* drivers and key variables for the combined policy scenarios.

3.1. Baseline

The Baseline scenario illustrates that without *IPAT*-related policy interventions, the interactions between dynamically changing drivers produce strongly non-linear and historically discontinuous patterns over the course of the 21st century for key global variables (Figure 2).

Growth in world population contributes to increasing environmental impacts until 2056 when world population reaches a peak at 8.75 billion people. Afterwards, the relative importance of the driver 'population' decreases as global population moderately but persistently declines to 7.76 billion by 2100 (Figure 2a).

Affluence, on the other hand, grows continuously to reach a value of 42,410 (2019-)€ of annual final demand per capita by 2091, which is 4.3 times as high as the initial value (Figure 2b).

However, in the last decades of the simulation affluence levels begin to decline sharply and at an accelerated rate, reaching about 21,690 € in 2110.

The role of technological development is reflected in Figure 2c and d. Until affluence levels begin to stagnate and decline at the beginning of the 2090s, we can observe affluence-driven improvements in production technologies that result in a continuous decrease in environmental impacts per unit of production. Thus, energy intensities and the intensity at which five important minerals (copper, lead, nickel, silver, zinc) are used by the global economy decline by approximately 59%, 58%, 65%, 63%, 43% and 65%, respectively.

CO₂ exhibits a 56% decline by 2091, aside from a localized increase linked to deforestation. Nonetheless, in the simulation's final decades, this downward trend is reversed as reductions in affluence contribute to a deterioration of efficiency parameters.

Consequently, in the Baseline scenario affluence is the main driver of environmental impacts during most of the simulation time, with population growth playing a minor but still significant role. The relative contribution of 'bad' production technologies to environmental degradation decreases throughout the scenario which counterbalances increasing population and affluence levels. However, technological development does not occur fast enough to stabilize or reverse environmental impacts: material extraction rises continuously throughout the simulation (Figure 2f), as well as energy use and cumulative GHG emissions (Figure 2e). In combination with increasing natural GHG emissions due to positive feedback loops within the climate system, the anthropogenic emissions lead to a temperature increase of 4.7 °C relative to 1850 at the end of the simulation, compared to 1.09 °C in 2019.

While feedback mechanisms from material extraction or temperature increases are not at work in the Baseline scenario, the increasing depletion of fossil fuel reserves and resources leads to a worsening of the fossil energy return on energy invested, and, in general, to increasing input requirements of the fossil sectors, which from 2088 onward can no longer be counteracted by affluence-driven technological efficiency improvements (Figure 2g). Given the continued reliance of the global economy on great quantities of fossil fuel inputs, increasing extraction difficulties cause global output to decline (Figure 2h). This activates a self-reinforcing feedback loop: as output declines, affluence levels drop, which worsens the environmental impacts of production technologies, reinforcing the biophysical constraints on economic production.

Figure 2: Key outputs of the Baseline scenario: evolution of (a) world population, (b) global average final demand per capita, (c) energy and emission intensities of output, (d) material intensity of output for copper, lead, nickel, silver and zinc, (e) cumulative final energy use and emissions (including land use change emissions), (f) cumulative material extraction for copper, lead, nickel, silver and zinc, (g) fossil energy input requirements of the fossil energy sector, (h) global output and (i) global average temperature compared to the pre-industrial period during the simulation.

3.2. Population policy scenario (PPI)

The PPI scenario shows that a reduction of the driver ‘population’ can significantly change the evolution of the other components of IPAT and avoid a decline in affluence due to fossil depletion during the simulation period but is insufficient to stabilize or reverse environmental degradation.

As an immediate consequence of the population policy world population declines throughout the 21st century and reaches 3.25 billion in 2100, a number comparable to world population in 1964 (Figure 3a). At the same time, affluence levels increase faster than in the Baseline scenario

and by 2100 exceed 45,000 €, which also speeds up the improvement of production technologies (Figure 3b-d). By 2110, energy intensity has declined by 64%, and GHG emission intensity by 61%, 5 percentage points more than in the Baseline scenario. GHG intensity declines less than energy intensity because emissions include greenhouse gases other than CO₂ whose emission intensities decline more slowly. Material intensities also drop faster—by 66%, 75%, 73%, 47%, and 74% by 2110 for copper, lead, nickel, silver, and zinc, respectively. Unlike in the baseline scenario, technological progress maintains its positive trajectory throughout the entire simulation. The continuous reduction in the size of the global population, driven by low birth rates, enables affluence levels to increase even though global output peaks in 2070.

Nevertheless, several indicators suggest that the population policy intervention is insufficient to lead to long-term sustainability beyond the 21st century: From 2065 onward, the rate of improvements in the fossil sector declines and growth in final demand slows down while environmental impacts, represented by cumulative material extraction and emissions, continue to increase (Figure 3e-g). In 2110, the global economy is situated in a 3.56 °C warmer and significantly older world due to the population policy intervention: the average age of the population in the formal economy is 53 in the center and the semiperiphery, and 52 in the periphery, while it was 41, 36 and 28 in 2019. The combined pressure on the working force stemming from climate-change-induced labor productivity losses and from the need to support a higher share of population beyond the working age, could lead to major economic reproduction problems beyond the simulation period.

Figure 3: Key outputs of the PPI scenario: evolution of (a) world population, (b) global average final demand per capita, (c) energy and emission intensities of output, (d) material intensity of output for copper, lead, nickel, silver and zinc, (e) cumulative final energy use and emissions (including land use change emissions), (f) cumulative material extraction for copper, lead, nickel, silver and zinc, (g) fossil energy input requirements of the fossil energy sector, (h) global output and (i) global average temperature compared to the pre-industrial period during the simulation.

3.3. Sufficiency scenario (SPI)

While affluence is an important driver of environmental impacts in the Baseline scenario, and the main driver of impacts in the PPI scenario, in the SPI simulation, it plays a less significant role. Instead, during the first half of the simulation, the importance of population as driver increases, while during the second half of the simulation, environmentally harmful production technologies become the main driver of degradation, as affluence levels of the world regions and classes converge, and world population declines from a maximum of 8.55 billion in 2049 to 6.6

billion people at the end of the simulation (Figure 4a-d). The convergence of affluence to a relatively low level in the scenario has two main effects on the *P* and *T* drivers. On the one hand, affluence-induced declines in mortality rates are smaller than in fertility rates, eventually resulting in moderate population decline even at relatively low affluence levels. On the other hand, technological improvements are slower than in the Baseline and the PPI scenario, and, consequently, biophysical feedbacks on economic production via energy depletion manifest earlier (Figure 4c, d and g).

The SPI scenario performs worse than the PPI scenario but better than the baseline scenario in terms of absolute economic impacts, despite the inferior technological profile of the economy compared to the baseline: cumulative final energy use in the SPI scenario is 74% of final energy use in the baseline, while in PPI energy use is only 66% of the baseline value. This pattern is repeated for cumulative material extraction of copper, lead, nickel, silver and zinc, which is 80% (64%), 82%, (65%), 82% (65%), 76% (62%), 82% (65%) of the baseline value for the SPI (PPI) scenario. Nevertheless, the SPI scenario proves slightly more effective than the PPI scenario at limiting global warming due to a lower amount of GHG emissions other than CO₂, resulting in an increase of global average temperature of 3.54 °C compared to the pre-industrial period.

Thus, positive effects of increasing affluence levels on the *T* driver only translate into environmental impact reductions if they are combined with a population policy. Moreover, environmental impacts can be reduced via convergence policies that reduce the affluence of the richest classes and increase those of the poorest, even when assuming that the unintentional effect of convergence policies is a reduction or deterioration in technological development.

Figure 4: Key outputs of the SPI scenario: evolution of (a) world population, (b) global average final demand per capita, (c) energy and emission intensities of output, (d) material intensity of output for copper, lead, nickel, silver and zinc, (e) cumulative final energy use and emissions (including land use change emissions), (f) cumulative material extraction for copper, lead, nickel, silver and zinc, (g) fossil energy input requirements of the fossil energy sector, (h) global output and (i) global average temperature compared to the pre-industrial period during the simulation.

3.4. Efficiency scenario (EPI)

The EPI scenario essentially reproduces the patterns observed in the Baseline scenario although the higher rates of efficiency improvement allow the system to grow for a slightly longer period than in the Baseline scenario (Figure 5).

While the size of the world population peaks in the same year and at the same value as in the baseline, final demand per capita continues to grow until 2094, becoming the most significant driver of environmental impacts in the scenario. Nevertheless, the peak of 44,229 € of annual final demand per capita is still lower than the affluence achieved in the PPI scenario. Given the assumed link between rising affluence levels and rising technological sufficiency, the

technology-related variables in the EPI scenario generally improve more than in the baseline and in the SPI scenario but less than in the PPI scenario. Energy and GHG emission intensities decline one percentage point more than in the baseline, while the additional decline in material intensities compared to the baseline scenario is between -1 (silver) and +2 (nickel) percentage points.

Nevertheless, at the end of the simulation, the emergence of discontinuous non-linear developments can be observed. Affluence and output start to decline sharply and technological developments reach critical turning points (Figure 5c, d, g) indicating that even with higher political efforts to foster efficiency, the fundamentally unsustainable character of a business-as-usual development pathway as represented by the Baseline scenario cannot be altered. In the EPI scenario, global temperatures rise even more than in the baseline - to 4.74 °C by 2110 - despite a transition to 100% renewable electricity.

Figure 5: Key outputs of the EPI scenario: evolution of (a) world population, (b) global average final demand per capita, (c) energy and emission intensities of output, (d) material intensity of output for copper, lead, nickel, silver and zinc, (e) cumulative final energy use and emissions (including land use change emissions), (f) cumulative material extraction for copper, lead, nickel, silver and zinc, (g) fossil energy input requirements of the fossil energy sector, (h) global output and (i) global average temperature compared to the pre-industrial period during the simulation.

3.5. Combined scenarios

Unsurprisingly, all combined scenarios with a population policy element (PPI+SPI, PPI+EPI, PPI+SPI+EPI) display highly similar population trajectories, with only marginal differences in the final values (2.6 billion in 2110 for PPI+SPI and PPI+SPI+EPI; 2.66 billion in 2110 for PPI+EPI). Conversely, the combination of sufficiency and efficiency policies (SPI+EPI) results in the same population in 2110 as the isolated SPI scenario (6.6 billion in 2110) (Figure 6a).

The PPI+EPI scenario produces a continuously increasing global affluence level (about 52,000 € per capita in 2110) while in the rest of the combined scenarios, affluence in the different regions and classes converges to around 15,400 € (Figure 6b).

Regarding the T driver, the comparison of the combined policy interventions clearly shows that higher technological efficiency is not an indicator of lower environmental impacts (Figure 6c-g). The PPI+EPI scenario displays the most pronounced declines in energy, emission and material intensities as well as in the input requirements of the fossil sectors but nevertheless has the second highest environmental impacts, i.e. cumulative energy use, emissions and material extraction. Only the SPI+EPI scenario produces slightly higher environmental impacts, displaying also the least efficient technology profile. The PPI+SPI scenario and the scenario that addresses all three drivers follow comparable trajectories, with the latter displaying both faster technological development and lower environmental impacts, due to the assumed accelerating effects of efficiency policies on technological progress.

In the combined scenarios with SPI element, output declines due to declining affluence levels, while in combined scenarios with PPI element output declines to prevent labor scarcity from arising (Figure 6h). The finding that technological efficiency improvements do not translate into declining output levels and do not necessarily translate into a decline in impacts, illustrates the existence of rebound effects through which gains in technological efficiency are directly translated into affluence and/or population increases.

The lowest global temperature increase occurs in the PPI+SPI+EPI scenario where global warming is limited to 2.83 °C while in the PPI+SPI scenario the global average temperature increase is 2.85 °C (Figure 6i). Both values are considerably smaller than the most successful 'isolated' policy intervention (i.e., 3.56 °C in the PPI scenario). Thus, the combination of population intervention policies with additional policies, especially those that foster sufficiency of richer classes and world regions, constitutes a significantly more effective climate policy approach than those strategies that only address one component of *IPAT*. Likewise, we find that a global one-child policy in the simulation yields climate outcomes comparable to a global sufficiency intervention that leads final demand per capita to converge around 15,000 €, irrespective of efficiency policies.

The range of projected global warming over the baseline scenario and all policy scenarios is 2.83 °C to 4.74 °C which shows the crucial importance of climate policies that address more than only the 'technology' driver of the *IPAT* equation. However, even the scenario combining policy interventions that jointly address all three drivers of environmental impacts is far from reaching international climate policy goals.

Figure 6: Key outputs of the combined policy scenarios (PPI+SPI, PPI+EPI, SPI+EPI, PPI+SPI+EPI): Evolution of (a) world population, (b) global average final demand per capita, (c) energy and emission intensities of output, (d) material intensity of output for copper and silver, (e) cumulative final energy use and emissions (including land use change emissions), (f) cumulative material extraction for copper and silver, (g) fossil energy input requirements of the fossil energy sector, (h) global output and (i) global average temperature compared to the pre-industrial period during the simulations. The development of material intensity and cumulative material extraction for lead, nickel and zinc are displayed in Suppl. Figure 1 and 2.

Considering all the simulated scenarios, we can summarize the findings in three main insights: First, all components of *IPAT* influence each other in dynamic ways. Consequently, isolated approaches to society-economy-environment problems are incapable of providing an accurate understanding of the problem. Second, without policy interventions or other intentional societal changes, the interactions between drivers, rather than ‘solving’ the sustainability problem, lead to escalating environmental impacts whose feedbacks on the economic system result in economic collapse. Last, policy interventions that go beyond policy-induced production

efficiency increases by addressing the drivers 'population', and - to a lesser extent - 'affluence' can significantly reduce environmental impacts but are far from reducing pressure on the environment to levels that can be expected to be sustainable in the long-term.

4. Discussion

4.1. Possible biases in scenario assumptions

As in every scenario study, scenario assumptions regarding key parameters shape simulation outcomes, jointly with the model structure and data. Thus, we want to highlight some possible biases in the assumptions made, and discuss to which extent changes in the assumptions could alter the main insights obtained (section 3.5).

We identify one 'pessimist' bias and three 'optimist' biases:

First, the mitigation potential of technology-focused policies could be underestimated as we take a rather conservative approach to the possibility of accelerating technological efficiency gains through policy interventions, due to the uncertainty about the rate at which technological progress can be accelerated by policy interventions (cf. section 4.2). Thus, we assume only a 5% improvement in the technological impact factor at a given level of affluence, and 'only' simulate the effects of a complete greening of the electricity sector while we do not consider policy interventions that would electrify great parts of current non-electric energy inputs. Instead, in the EPI as well as in the Baseline scenario, not more than 25% of the 2019 values for non-electric energy inputs to key economic sectors is replaced by green electricity. Likewise, we do not simulate technologies whose scalability is questionable, such as carbon capture and storage or different types of geoengineering (Braun et al., 2025; Sekera & Lichtenberger, 2020; Wewerinke-Singh et al., 2022).

This relatively conservative stance in the EPI scenario is offset by highly optimistic assumptions across all scenarios that may reflect an excessive confidence in technological progress.

First, the theoretical possibility of complete decoupling of both energy and materials from production growth at high affluence levels is highly questionable and likely overestimates the energy and material efficiency gains in all scenarios. The estimation error could be even higher if we take into account that all scenarios are driven by continuous increases in labor productivity, which are linked to increases in exergy, counteracting exergy efficiency increases that are ultimately constrained by thermodynamic limits (Furse, 2025).

Second, the inclusion of only one biophysical feedback from I to P , A and T possibly results in an overestimation of the period of time in which the system can grow before it collapses: we do neither include climate damages on economic output (Diaz & Moore, 2017; Lenton et al., 2023), nor feedbacks on the economic system triggered by land use changes and biodiversity losses (Giglio et al., 2024; Markandya, 2015). Also, we assume that there are no limits to mineral extraction. Although the latter depend on assumptions about ultimately recoverable resources (URR) and there is no imminent threat of depletion during the 21st century for none of the five

minerals included for the URR value we adopt (Henckens, 2021), the adverse economic effects of increasing input requirements resulting from falling ore grades are not depicted in the model.

Last, assumptions regarding land use productivity increases are optimistic as they assume annual productivity increases of 1.73% throughout the century irrespective of the *IPAT* drivers, and do not take into account the negative impact of soil erosion, biodiversity loss and other environmental impacts on land productivity (Bouchoms et al., 2019; FAO, 2022; Hossain et al., 2020).

Taking all biases into account, we find that the ‘techno-optimist’ tendencies in our analysis exceed those that could be characterized as ‘techno-pessimist’ or ‘techno-realist. However, correcting for these biases by reducing techno-optimism would affirm, rather than contradict the key scenario results: (1) it would reinforce the feedback of environmental impacts (*I*) on the drivers (*P-A-T*) which would illustrate the bidirectionality of the *IPAT* framework in all the policy scenarios rather than only in the Baseline and in the EPI scenario; (2) it would lead to an even earlier collapse of economic output in the Baseline scenario, and (3) it would likely lower the mitigation effect of policy scenarios.

4.2. Feasibility of policy scenarios

An *IPAT*-based approach to policy interventions systematically considers policy options that address population and affluence as drivers of environmental degradation, apart from policies aiming at an improvement of production technologies. Although the latter is commonly given a central importance in techno-optimistic environmental policy discourses (Engström & Kolk, 2024; Leipold et al., 2019) our simulations show that the former policy options should not be neglected in environmental policy-making.

Nevertheless, there might be a trade-off between policy effectiveness and policy feasibility (Verhoef et al., 1996) for *IPAT*-related problems: population policies are barely discussed in the sustainability context since the UN Conference on Population and Development in Cairo marked the beginning of a ‘population taboo’ (O’Sullivan, 2020). Rather it is often assumed that education and access to contraceptives linked to increasing affluence will reduce population pressures. Although our analysis relies heavily on this hypothesis, we also show that affluence-driven changes in world population are insufficient to stabilize or even alleviate environmental impacts and that significant reductions in impact, in the absence of technological breakthroughs, are only achieved by relatively ‘radical’ population policies such as a globally implemented one-child policy which is maintained throughout the simulation. Apart from the current low support for such policies at the global level, an additional feasibility restriction stems from the requirement of high labor productivity improvements that have to be maintained throughout the century to counteract the loss of labor force due to an aging population.

Sufficiency policies are increasingly discussed in the academic context and beyond (Alexander & Rutherford, 2019; Kallis et al., 2024; Samadi et al., 2017) but have not yet entered the mainstream discourse (Koch, 2020). Thus, although the political feasibility of sufficiency approaches to sustainability problems might increase, it is questionable whether social classes of high-income countries would agree to degrow their consumption between 3.56% (for the richest 20% of the population) and 0,19% (for the poorest 30% of the population) per year.

Policies fostering efficiency arguably align well with currently dominant narratives of ecological modernization and green governmentality (Bäckstrand & Lövbrand, 2019) but in our scenario

play only a complementary role and, without additional policies, barely change the baseline trajectory. While our simulation shows that technology policies aiming at a 100% renewable electricity system do not achieve significant reductions in environmental impacts, the modeling of the effects of more abstract technology-centered policies is highly uncertain. Although policies can have a certain influence on the direction of technological development (Hémous & Olsen, 2021; Mazzucato et al., 2020), it is evident that faster and larger-scale politically motivated changes in production technologies encounter greater implementation challenges, thereby limiting the practical feasibility of these policies.

Thus, the scenarios – especially those with an SPI or PPI component – should be seen as stylized policy scenarios designed to determine their maximum effects. Very likely, even under favorable institutional conditions, the implementation of SPI- or PPI-related policies would be less radical than in the simulations.

4.3. Underlying institutional conditions

The development of P, A, T and I does not take place in abstract space but is shaped and constrained by underlying institutional conditions constituting the current world order.

First, population policies are designed in the context of the (nation) state and are subject to strategic national interests: assuming that states are interested in maintaining or increasing power and that a higher population generally translates into a higher working force and a higher pool of potential soldiers as well as a greater share in global environmental commons (Coleman & Rowthorn, 2011; McNicoll, 1999) we can hypothesize that states in the current world order will try to increase rather than decrease birth rates, or at least not decrease birth rates at a higher rate than other states, which considerably restricts possible policy-based development trajectories of the P driver.

Second, wealth is linked to power and technological capacity (Jovetic & Katnic, 2024), and dominant cultures and narratives promote a continued increase rather than decrease in affluence (Schmelzer, 2017, 2024), which makes sufficiency policy strategies potentially incompatible with the current world order.

Third, technology is not an isolated subsystem of the world system, nor is the direction of its development neutral. Instead, it is deeply shaped by—and entangled with—existing political, economic, and cultural power structures, reflected for example in the links between civil and military innovations (Bordin et al., 2020) and in rebound effects that undermine gains in resource efficiency (Vélez-Henao et al., 2019). Moreover, short-term and linear thinking, aligning with and fostered by dominant ways of life and values, can lead to technological fixes that exacerbate unsustainable trajectories. Last, large-scale technological transformations such as the global energy transition have deep implications on the shape of the current world order as they change geopolitical and economic power relationships (Hafner & Tagliapietra, 2020; Y. Yang et al., 2023).

From this perspective, the effect of I on $P-A-T$ can be seen as the reduction of the capacity of the material structures, 'rules of the game', and dominant ideas of the current civilization to reproduce themselves over time.

Thus, we stress the need for greater attention in future work to the deeper institutional conditions underlying the $IPAT$ framework—factors not directly captured in our modeling study.

These conditions offer an alternative lens for assessing policy effectiveness and underscore the necessity of broader systemic change on the global level to expand the option space for environmental and economic policies.

5. Conclusion

While traditional approaches to *IPAT* have tended to focus on single drivers of environmental degradation, in this paper, we have used the MORDRED-IAM to simulate a business-as-usual scenario as well as various policy scenarios that reflect the complex and dynamic nature of the *IPAT* framework. Going beyond the commonly assumed unidirectionality of the equation, with *P*, *A*, and *T* driving *I*, we have shown that as a consequence of environmental degradation caused by the economy, *P*, *A* and *T* themselves can be deeply affected by emerging feedbacks from the biophysical system affecting the development possibilities of the social system. Formalizing the interdependencies between the components of *IPAT* through an IAM has enabled us to shed light on the role different drivers play in environmental degradation and to systematically compare the effectiveness of various isolated and combined policy options formulated with the *IPAT* framework. Although our work illustrates the continued relevance of *IPAT* for current environmental and sustainability-related problems, the limited success in terms of environmental outcomes of the policy scenarios points to the need of deep and fast systemic transformations on the global level and corresponding scientific analyses of sustainability-related problems that move beyond population, affluence and technology to address the underlying institutional drivers of unsustainability ingrained in the current world order.

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